

USE OF CR-39 SOLID STATE NUCLEAR TRACK DETECTORS IN ASSESSMENT OF THE RADON EXPOSURE IN TWO LIMESTONE CAVES IN ROMANIA

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Abstract. Radon concentration measurements were carried out using solid-state nuclear track-etch detectors (RSKS) type CR-39 in Polovragi and Muierilor limestone caves from Eastern Carpathian (Romania). Two campaigns for measurements were performed in each cave (winter and spring seasons). The time-periods for which measurements were performed provide reliable data for estimating the dose exposure to the radon for tourist guides.

Higher radon levels were measured in Polovragi cave in the spring season, 3331 Bq m⁻³ being the highest value. In this cave the gradual accumulation of radon further and deeper into the cave in the absence of air movement inside the cave was demonstrated. Muierilor cave is characterized by slightly variation of radon concentration through the caves caused probably by the high air movement inside the cave. Some anomalies were recorded in several measurement points probably due to the local conditions.

Key words: CR-39 detector, radon, cave, effective dose, geology

1. INTRODUCTION

Radon is an odourless and colourless radioactive, noble gas, continually generated from rocks. It has relatively short half-life (3.8 days). Being an intermediate daughter in the ²³⁸U – ²⁰⁶Pb radioactive decay chain, the radon has very reactive decay products that can be attached to aerosol particles and partly deposited on the walls of the respiratory tract and inside the human lung during inhalation process. Due to its short half-life it decays inside the lung, damaging the tissue [1]. From this reason, radon is considered the second most important cause of lung cancer, after smoking [2-5]. The radon studies have also implication in other interesting applications [6-9].

Therefore, in underground workspaces such as karst caves, an elevated exposure to radon may be expected, mainly for touristic guides and exposure assessment proves to be necessary. The measurement of radon levels and comparison of these with international health standards provides guidance with respect to workers safety.

Radon concentration in caves varies widely depending on many factors. Geology is the most important factor that controls the source and distribution of radon. The amount of radon released from rocks is mainly controlled by the types of minerals in which uranium occur and its migration and accumulation are controlled by the transmission characteristic of the bedrock, the type of the carrier fluids including carbon dioxide gas and groundwater, meteorological parameters such as barometric pressure, relative humidity and temperature. In addition, cave peculiarities, ventilation in particular, are very important for radon accumulation. In general, diffusion is the dominant mechanism in the intergranular channels, capillaries and smaller pores; while in the larger pores and fractures, transport may become important or even dominant.

Caves, in all their aspects related to the radon concentration have aroused the interest of scientists. Therefore, many studies have been performed in order to estimate effective doses for workers and cave visitors [10-17], to establish a relation between radon concentration in cave with different issues like seasonal fluctuation [18, 19], geology [10, 20], outside air temperature [21] a.o.

In Romania, a country with a high karst potential due to the widespread of limestone rocks in many areas, radon-related studies began to be carried out relative recently. The studies are related to the distribution of radon concentration in two types of underground environments from Romania (cave and salt mine) [22], seasonal and diurnal variations of radon in caves [23]. For both studies CR-39 detectors and devices for continuous measurements have been used.

The aims of this study consisted in performing radon measurement throughout the two caves from southern Carpathians in order to determine radon air cave concentration, highlighting the seasonal variation and estimating the preliminary effective doses to which tour guides are exposed.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Radon concentration measurement

CR-39 detectors, type RSKS solid-state nuclear track-etch detectors, were used for radon concentration measurements. This type of detector is based on CR-39 plastic chips, placed under the cap of a cylindrical diffusion chamber sensitive to radon activity. Chemically is known as poly-allyl-diglycol carbonate or Columbia Resin. CR-39 is a light transparent plastic material with a refractive index of 1.498, used in the manufacture of spectacle lenses and much harder than polymethyl methacrylate although not quite as hard as glass.

The CR-39 is a commercially available, optically clear, amorphous, thermoset plastic in which nuclear particle tracks can be revealed by etching in a hot NaOH solution. Its uniformity of response (< 1% variation), high sensitivity and optical quality make it ideal for identification of mass and charge of nuclear particles and for other applications.

The measurement protocol was made in compliance with quality assurance and control programs proposed by HPA-NRPB or other European authorities [24].

The detectors were placed in the main passageways of the caves for about three months, in two different seasons: winter (November-March: 2012/13 and 2014/15) and spring (March-June 2013 and 2015), respectively.

All detectors were etched in optimal etching conditions experimentally determined for 4.5 hours by using a solution of 6.25 molar NaOH at a temperature of 90⁰ C. After etching process, the detectors were subsequently washed with warm distilled water and then were neutralized for 30 min in a 1% hydrochloric acid-distilled water solution and dried. The automatic reading and counting of tracks were performed under an optical transmission light microscope component part of equipment Radometer 2000 (produced by RadoSys from Hungary).

Radon concentration (C_{Rn}) were calculated by the following relation:

$$C_{Rn} = \frac{(\rho \cdot F)}{t} \quad (1)$$

where C_{Rn} is radon concentration expressed in Bq m⁻³, ρ represents the track density expressed in tracks mm⁻², F is the calibration factor, provided by the manufacturer, expressed in (kBq h m⁻³)/ (tracks mm⁻²) and t is exposure time expressed in h.

2.2. Measurement sites

Polovragi and Muierilor caves are limestone caves located in the central part of Romania (Fig.1), on the south-facing slope of Căpățâni Mountains, respectively Parâng Mountains from Southern Carpathians. Olteț and Galbenului rivers carved a Tithonic-Neocomian limestone pile and build-up Oltețului, respectively Galbenului Gorges whose left, respectively right slopes host the caves. This limestone pile appears on 1-1,5 km in width and 12 km in length, on the south-facing slope of Căpățâni Mountains and also in Parâng Mountains divided from the last ones by the Olteț River.

Figure 1 - The location of studied caves on the sketch-map of Romania

Detectors were placed through the main passageways of studied caves, from the entrance to the deepest (Fig. 2, Fig. 3), in easily accessible points within each cave. The number and distribution of detectors were chosen taking into account the peculiarities of caves and the aim of the study. Six detectors were used

for each cave in 2012/2013 campaign respectively, nine-ten for 2014/2015 campaign.

2.2.1. Polovragi Cave

Polovragi cave is subterranean meander of the Olteț river that corresponds to the lower one of the two fluvial erosional bench from Oltețului Gorges. It includes three distinct levels that develop over more than 9 km of passages. The two upper levels are inactive while the lower one is carrying a stream [25]. In the upper level, Polovragi cave consists of a main passage with more branches and 3 sections, whose length available for tourists is about 900 m. The width and height of the passages vary through these sections by decreasing sizes upstream. Inside the cave, walls are coated with flowstone and in some sectors there are many stalagmites and stalactites growing from the floor and ceiling.

The cave is typically wet, leaking through airflows, the mean temperature being of about 8°C, with small variations over the seasons.

Figure 2 - Map of Polovragi cave

2.2.2. Muierilor Cave

Muierilor cave consists of an underground passageways system disposed on four levels, the upper level only being exploited through tourism (Fig. 3). The general development of the whole system is NNV-SSE, following the direction of one important fault line. The cave clearly represents successive captures of a part of Galbenul River along this fracture. The genesis of the cave passages has probably paralleled in time with the creation of the gorge. This evolution ends up very close to the granitic basement overlaid by the limestone, where the river left the

underground path. Further on, the karstification processes were carried on by percolation water from the surface.

Figure 3 - Map of Muierilor cave

2.3. Estimation of dose based on radon exposure inside the caves

To evaluate a potential health hazards and radon risk exposure caused by inhaling radon and its daughter products inside the cave, the effective doses have been estimated based on radon concentrations measured in each cave by applying the equation of [12]:

$$E_{Rn} = C_{Rn} \cdot F \cdot t \cdot d \cdot u \quad (2)$$

where: E_{Rn} = effective dose (mSv y^{-1}); C_{Rn} = the average radon concentration inside the cave air (Bq m^{-3}); F = the average radon equilibrium factor between radon and the decay products; t represents the time spent inside the cave by the professionals, like investigators or guides (h y^{-1}); d = dose conversion factor of 1.4 for workers (mSv/mJ hm^{-3}) and u is the unit factor of 5.6×10^{-6} ($\text{mJ hm}^{-3} / \text{Bqm}^{-3}$).

For the equilibrium factor between radon and its progeny has been considered the value of 0.57, calculated by [26] based on large number of data reported from global caves. For the time spent inside the cave by the professionals, a cumulated period of time not exceeding 250 h/year/guide has been taken into account.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of study reveal different values of radon concentration in Polovragi and Muierilor caves during the monitored time-periods. Taking into account the fact that radon concentration in caves depends on several factors like geology, meteorological parameters and cave particularities this variability is expected. Moreover, the two measurement campaigns in each cave cover more than half

calendar year and provide reliable data for estimating the dose exposure for tourist guides.

The radon concentrations, including average of those obtained for winter and spring seasons, in the first campaigns are presented in Table 1. Furthermore, Table 2 contains the results for the second campaign.

Table 1
Radon concentrations (Bq.m-3) at different locations within the caves and mean radon concentration for investigated period (first campaign)

Measurement points	Radon concentration [Bq.m-3]										
	Nov. 2012 – March 2013 (winter season)					March 2013 – June 2013 (spring season)				Nov. 2012- June 2013	
	Polovragi cave (P.c.)		Muierilor cave (M.c.)			Polovragi cave (P.c.)		Muierilor cave (M.c.)		P.c	M.c.
	Local value	Mean	Local value	Mean	Local value	Mean	Local value		Mean		
1	400	1166	1704	1527	1187	2591	●	1366	~1878	~1446	
2	550		1793		2543		●				
3	460		485		2690		180				
4	1618		1808		3331		1559				
5	1790		1846		2739		2597				
6	2178		●		3060		1129				

- Not reclaimed

The concentration increases toward the middle of the Polovragi cave (end of touristic path) in the winter season proving a gradual accumulation of radon inside the cave in the lack of air-flows. In the spring season, the values are higher than those from winter season but their distribution throughout the cave is much more uniform.

However, inside the Muierilor cave, the radon concentrations are more uniform in the winter season, existing a local anomaly (measurement point 3), confirmed in the spring season too, that could be influenced by an unfavourable context for radon measurements (ex: possible high local ventilation) or by the dimensions of this place (Turk Hall).

For Muierilor cave, the results showed that there was no significant difference between the radon concentration values from measurement points. In the same way, a seasonal variation in radon concentrations is insignificant. The arithmetic mean variation in the spring season was found to be close to that found in winter period. Opposite to seasonal difference in Polovragi cave between radon concentrations, highlighting higher values for spring season, in Muierilor cave, an increase in values in the spring season, as would be expected, is not documented. In both campaigns, a thus reversed seasonal pattern is showed. This pattern could

be due to the high air-flows circulation inside the Muierilor cave in conditions of some little differences between inside and outside air temperatures.

Table 2
Radon concentrations (Bq.m-3) at different locations within the caves and mean radon concentration for investigated period (second campaign)

Measurement points	Radon concentration [Bq.m-3]										
	Nov. 2014 – March 2015 (winter season)					March 2015 – June 2015 (spring season)				Nov. 2014-June 2015	
	Polovragi cave (P.c.)		Muierilor cave (M.c.)			Polovragi cave (P.c.)		Muierilor cave (M.c.)		P.c.	M.c.
	Local value	Mean	Local value	Mean	Local value	Mean	Local value	Mean	Mean		
1	41	729	1041	1414	524	1636	803	754	~1182	~1084	
2	192		1734		1233		1015				
3	376		1295		1618		820				
4	548		2946		1677		•				
5	1052		1123		2088		443				
6	901		1114		1861		669				
7	1036		1176		1889		734				
8	1042		1127		1886		696				
9	1367		1167		1952		852				
10	•		1041		-		-				

• Not reclaimed

In the second campaign the previous tendency of gradual accumulation of radon inside the cave is mainly kept. In the measurement point 5, the value appears to be influenced by local factors (ex. cracks). In the same time, the seasonal variation of radon concentration was detected. Increasing values in the spring season for Polovragi cave and a decreasing trend in the same season for Muierilor cave were documented.

If comparing our results with those from other countries, like Hungary, Spain, Slovenia, UK, Brazil etc., similarities were noticed. [27] measured radon concentration up to 7,000 Bq m⁻³ (summer) in the Pál-völgy Cave (Hungary), which is carved in Eocene limestone. Significantly lower values were recorded during the winter season (200 – 300 Bq m⁻³), which cause the annual average to be around 1,900 Bq m⁻³.

In Altamira Cave (Spain), the annual value is higher (3,562 Bq m⁻³) [28] than in the Hungarian cave, with the highest registered concentration during the summer and spring period. They assume that radon is emitted by the rocks surrounding the cave and from the clayish cave sediments.

A similar situation was noticed in the Postojna Cave, but with concentrations that range from 200 to 3,000 Bq m⁻³ [15], values that are rather similar (slightly higher) to our measurements.

Generally, the radon concentration values from Polovragi and Muierilor caves are the highest values measured until now in Romanian caves. Mean winter radon values were reported [23] from Cetății cave ($52 \pm 38 \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$), Urșilor cave ($393 \pm 175 \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$), Meziad ($112 \pm 91 \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$), Cloșani ($447 \pm 262 \text{ Bqm}^{-3}$).

Geological background could be considered one of the reasons of these relative high radon levels in caves.

The limestone pile that host Polovragi and Muierilor caves represents the sedimentary cover of the pre-Alpine basement consisting mainly of metamorphic rocks and granitoids. The metamorphic rocks sequence in the Danubian basement of our study area belongs to the Lainici-Păiuș terrane. This consists of metasedimentary rocks (marble, different types of gneiss and amphibolite) characterised by low pressure/high temperature conditions [22]. Numerous granitoid plutons intrude the Lainici - Păiuș terrane, such intrusive bodies in our study area are the Neoproterozoic Olteț and Novaci granitoid plutons situated under the Thitonic-Neocomian limestone. Knowing that acid magmatic rock such granite and granitoids are ones of the most radioactive rocks, those could be considered important radon sources in this area. In the same time, rocks that contain significant proportions of flaky minerals, usually oriented in rock mass, such micaschists, limit the vertical movement of radon and consequently, its entering into underground spaces. The lack of pores and intergranular channels in limestone rocks makes that diffusion mechanism of radon to be limited and transport, which in turn depends on the presence of fractures and faults in the rock mass, to constitute the main mechanism by which radon can reach to accumulate in caves. Thereby, in the basement of our areas, with these types of rocks and their characteristics is created a balance in terms of generation/migration of radon.

With respect to the potential health hazards caused by inhaling radon by the tour guides working in Polovragi and Muierilor caves, based on the mean radon concentration found in each location, the effective doses have been estimated by using the equation present above. Important for this reason is the exposure period, respectively the time spent in the cave that is different from season to season. Taking into account, the timetable of caves, we calculate about 250 h/year/guide. Applying the E_m equation the effective doses received by tour guides were obtained (1.7 mSv.y^{-1}) respectively (1.41 mSv.y^{-1}) for Polovragi and Muierilor caves. These preliminary results show that in the second campaign were obtained smaller values: with 40% in the case of Polovragi cave and with 25% for Muierilor cave. These differences can be explained considering that meteorological parameters (average temperature, pluviometric regime, atmospheric pressure stability, etc) had different sequences in these two years. More, these results must be considered as preliminary because they not include measurements from summer season when is expected higher radon concentrations.

Dose evaluation in workplaces with potentially elevated radon exposure is compulsory and workers with annual dose higher than 1 mSv y^{-1} are defined as occupationally exposed to radiation [29]. Based on our estimates, in 64% of the monitored sites inside the two caves, the doses are higher than this level.

According to these results, we can determine the number of hours per month that a researcher or a guide should spend inside the cave, in order to respect the accepted limit and remain healthy. During the winter period, the professional

exposure in Polovragi Cave must be limited less than 16 h/ month and respectively, less than 7 h/ month during the summer season.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Radon concentration in the two show caves from Southern Carpathians using long-term measurements with CR-39 indicates: (1) *higher values compared with other Romanian caves* until now determined; (2) *similarities with caves from other countries* (Hungary, Spain, Slovenia, UK, Brazil. a.o.); (3) *seasonal variations of radon concentration* caves between the winter and spring seasons - in Muierilor cave the values indicate a seasonal variation with high concentration during the winter season and low concentrations during the spring season and in Polovragi cave radon values show a seasonal variation with low concentration during the winter season and higher concentrations during the spring season; (4) *radon concentration dependency to air-flow* - low air-flow in Polovragi cave leads to an increased concentration towards the centre of the cave and a generally higher concentration compared to Muierii cave where there is a higher air-flow; (5) *possible correlation of radon concentration with the regional geology* - the intrusive bodies in the Lainici - Păiuș terrane basement (Olteț and Novaci granitoid plutons) situated under the Thitonic-Neocomian limestone, can be taken into consideration from potential radon source; (6) *estimated dose for workplace exposure is higher than the 1 mSv y⁻¹* considered by [26]; (7) *great number of cave sites with higher than limit level doses* (64% of the monitored sites inside the two caves); (8) *requirements of reduce the working hours for guides inside the cave* in order to limited radon exposure of them.

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